
Tax Revenue and Macroeconomic Growth in Nigeria: A Contextual Analysis

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Author MI designed the study, performed the analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author TSTA managed the literature searches and performed the proofread. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims at evaluating the influence of tax revenue on the macroeconomic management of the Nigerian economy using a conceptual approach. By so doing, a comprehensive review of the literature as well as in-depth analysis of tax structure are critically conducted. Undeniably, an insight that shows a precise influence or relationship between tax revenue and the nation's growth can be regarded as a working tool for policymakers particularly in developing countries. In view of that, this paper explores the revenue trend in Nigeria for over three decades in relation to its effects on GDP growth. As shown by the literature, the existence of causal relationship between tax revenue and economic growth suggests the positive influence of taxation as a fiscal policy tool in enhancing macroeconomic growth. This is certainly the policy implication of Keynesian propositions. On the other hand, non-existence of causal relationship between tax revenue and economic growth implies that taxation as a fiscal variable shall be insignificant especially in the long run, as propounded by the Classical doctrine. In spite of the aforementioned policy importance, the percentage of tax revenue as a share of GDP in Nigeria remains positive but relatively low. This is attributed to the increased dependency of the economy on oil revenue while neglecting other potential sources

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especially in the areas of non-oil growth such as agriculture, solid minerals, and small-and-medium enterprises. However, this paper has established that tax revenue is an essential instrument for resource mobilisation and plays a positive and significant role towards sustainable growth and development of the Nigerian economy. Further evidence shows that tax revenue increases the size of public sector savings and produces higher returns which can be used to encourage the provision of infrastructural facilities that stimulates output growth in the economy. In view of that, there is a growing need for proactive measures within the Nigerian tax system to ensure full enforcement and compliance of tax regulations, proper monitoring and evaluation of tax procedures in order to fight corruption and strengthen accountability in the public sector management. There is also need to examine the link between the burden of these sources of revenue on taxpayers and the productivity of revenue to the government. The regulatory institutions responsible for handling tax related matters should be steered towards the need to re-design efficient and equitable tax policies capable of complementing public sector expenditure and hence, correct for the problems of ever-increasing deficit and debt which engendered enormous macroeconomic disequilibrium in the country.

Keywords: Tax revenue; macroeconomic growth; Keynesian view; Classical view.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mobilisation of domestic resources to provide long-term and sustainable growth is an essential policy option available to developing countries [1,2]. The most imperative instrument by which resources are mobilised and appropriately channelled to the government coffer is through the implementation of a feasible and effective tax revenue measures [3,4,5]. Failure to do so will result in seeking for domestic borrowing and external assistance, hence, as these measures would increase the vulnerability of the economy in terms of macroeconomic disequilibrium. Seeking for external assistance through borrowing from the multilateral corporations seems to be challenging and precarious given the high interest rate and restrictive conditions from the donor agencies. Moreover, other sources of domestic borrowing are limited due to poor private sector development or participation in the economic activities. Therefore, tax revenue remains the viable and productive measure through which government raise money for statutory functions and to finance other developmental responsibilities [6,7,2,8,9].

It is in view of this motivational background that this paper is basically aimed at evaluating the effects of tax revenue in contributing to sustainable growth in Nigeria. The study adopted a conceptual approach to explore the revenue trend for over three decades with the view to evaluate it effects on GDP growth. The focus is to provide better understanding of revenue growth by exposing the numerical values and further determine its influence on economic growth. As a result, the paper raised this simple question: is the capacity of revenue generation in Nigeria sufficient to encourage output growth?

However, one of the macroeconomic and fiscal challenges of the public sector administration in Nigeria is the gradual decline and deterioration in government revenue generation. This is evidenced by the annual increase in fiscal deficit and lack of sufficient capital stock to finance developmental projects and other social activities [10,7]. This indicates the growing need by the government to widen the revenue capacity for appropriate revenue mobilisation and encourage the contribution from non-oil revenue sources. As a constitutional function, it is the responsibility of the public sector to mobilise the productive revenue sources in all the nooks and crannies in order to avoid the future problem of fiscal imbalances. It is debated among the policy makers that, tax is one of the essential instrument with high potentials for increasing revenue generation in both developed and developing countries [11,12,13]. Apart from its significance as a major source of revenue, it also acts as a mechanism for regulating the tempo of economic and social activities in a given society [11,14].

Apart from public expenditure, one of the components of public sector economics that attracted much attention is the economic effect of government tax revenue towards economic growth. The relationship between tax revenue and economic growth has been one of the major debatable subjects that appear with a complex relationship in the public finance literature [15]. The difficulties emanate from the nature of the taxes themselves. This is because, certain taxes may be productive to the economy, while other taxes may have a distortionary effect on both the demand and supply-side of the economy, especially when imposed beyond the optimal

level [16,17,18,19]. In view of this inconsistency, the impact and positive influence of tax revenue on economic growth become uncertain and remains debatable. An understanding of the influence and causal link between tax revenue and nation's growth can be regarded as highly essential to policymakers and prospective private investors as it facilitates their decision making. If there is a causal relationship between tax revenue and economic growth, then, it suggests the positive influence of taxation in enhancing macroeconomic growth. This is certainly the policy implication of Keynesian propositions. On the other hand, if there is no causal relationship between tax revenue and economic growth, then, taxation shall be insignificant especially in the long run, as propounded by the Classical doctrine. In spite of the aforementioned policy importance, the literature has produced many conflicting results on the relationship between tax revenue and its impact on economic growth [15,17]. While an increasing number of studies supports the positive relationship, others show evidence in favour negative relationship.

Despite a number of several tax policy measures undertaken by the government to widen the revenue generation capacity, previous numerical evidence indicates that the percentage of tax revenue as a share of GDP is relatively low and remained insignificant, hence, the results of increased dependency of the Nigerian economy on oil revenue [20,21,6]. The problems of long-term sustainability of non-renewable resources, including oil and gas, has further generated the attention of policy makers and fiscal authorities in resource-dependent developing countries to explore other potential sources of revenue in order to avoid the future challenges of economic stagnation [21]. As hitherto indicated, it is against this context that this paper is designed to evaluate the effects of tax revenue in ensuring sustainable growth and development taking into cognisance the trend as well as the structure of revenue in Nigeria for more than three decades. The rest of this paper is therefore categorised as follows: section 2 examine and review the structure of the Nigerian tax profile from 1980 to 2015, section three deals with the empirical review of the literature taken into cognisance the divergent views and scholarly debates among numerous professionals on matters related to taxation, section four identifies the major problems and challenges of tax revenue management in Nigeria, and finally, section five contains the conclusion and policy recommendations on how efficiency and

productivity shall be maintained in the Nigerian tax system.

2. STRUCTURE AND REVIEW OF THE NIGERIAN TAX PROFILE

In Nigeria, the introduction of tax revenue as a means of generating income to the government has been in existence since before the amalgamation of northern and southern protectorates in 1914. A system in the form of direct tax was introduced and successfully implemented into the Northern part of Nigeria, as the citizens are already used to tax policies. Among which is the personal income tax ordinance introduced as far back as 1904 by the colonial administration and later metamorphose to direct tax. The direct tax was later introduced to the Western part of Nigeria in 1916 and to the eastern province in 1927. These tax legislations and other related laws are developed from the earlier colonial regulations. However, the success or otherwise of any tax system particularly in developing countries depends on the management policy and skilled labour force of the organisation. In Nigeria, Joint Tax Board (JTB) and Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) are established and designed to handle and report all tax related matters on behalf of the government.

The structure of the Nigerian tax revenue system focussed more attention on the proceeds derive from petroleum products and other trade-related items. While other potential sources of revenue like Value Added Tax and other tax bases are not given due consideration. This poor revenue mobilisation has exposed the weaknesses of economic policy and constrained the Nigerian economy in establishing a sound and efficient tax system in contrast to other sub-Saharan African countries [17,4]. With the recent increase in crisis in oil producing areas and global decline in the price of crude oil, other potential sources of revenue have demonstrated to be productive and reliable in generating significant resources needed to augment budgetary allocations in Nigeria. In addition, tax revenue is regarded among the essential component of public sector finance in Nigeria [2,9]. There are exists two categories of federally-collected tax revenue in Nigeria namely; (1) Oil revenue and (2) Non-oil revenue. The oil revenues are those returns from the exportation (sales) of crude oil and gas, receipts from petroleum profits tax and royalties, as well as revenue from the sales of domestic crude oil. On the other hand, non-oil revenues

are those revenue which encompasses returns from company income tax, property tax, value added tax, education tax, customs and excise duties, etc.

The desired level of revenue productivity is not yet attained in many developing economies given the nature of revenue structure in most of these countries. The rising trend of revenue is not consistent with the public expenditure, a situation that encouraged high fiscal imbalances between the demand-side and supply-side of government budgetary expenditures. This scenario is typical of the ideal circumstances witnessed in the Nigerian economy. The revenue profile of the Nigerian government as revealed in the statistical bulletin of [22] indicates that total revenue has considerably declined over the period, decreasing from ₦15.23 billion in 1980; to ₦13.29 billion in 1981; ₦11.43 billion in 1982; and ₦10.51 billion in 1983 (see Fig. 1). The decreased in aggregate government revenue was largely heighten by the economic recession that hit the global economy coupled with the overall decline in the crude oil price. Oil revenue in Nigeria accounted for over 70% of the aggregate revenue and a major component of the foreign earnings, hence the reason for the decline in total federally-collected revenue. From 1984, the value begins to increase up to ₦15.05 billion in 1985 and later decline to ₦12.60 billion in 1986. In preparation to implement the development strategy (Structural Adjustment

Programme: SAP) advocated by World Bank to developing countries, the value in 1987 increase rapidly to ₦25.38 billion; ₦27.60 billion in 1988; ₦53.87 billion in 1989 and ₦98.1 billion in 1990. The initial period of SAP is witnessed by an increase in the level of aggregate revenue in contrast to pre-SAP period. Subsequently, the aggregate value of total revenue begins to increased rapidly with over 100% initial increment from 1991 to 1999 where the value stood at ₦949.19 billion by the end of 1999. This may partly be as a result of various economic and complimentary reform programmes introduced during the planning period.

Supplementary dividends are expected to surface the economy with the transition and change from the governing style of military dictators to a much-celebrated democratic arrangement. In the year 2000, tax revenue stood at ₦1,906.16 billion, it then later increases from ₦2,231.60 billion in 2001 to an average of ₦7,866.59 billion in 2008. Though, these increase trend in tax revenue has not reflected on the life of an average Nigerian given the rising trend of the poverty level and unemployment rate in spite of a corresponding increase in total government expenditure during that period. By the fiscal year 2009, total federally collected revenue was valued at ₦4, 844.59 billion, this trend continues up to the last quarter of 2015 where it recorded an annual amount of ₦6,912.50 billion [22]. The prevalence and

Fig. 1. Trend of aggregate revenue in Nigeria

continuous increase in the level of debt and deficit indicate that the contribution of total revenue to ensure budgetary balance within the Nigerian public finance is insignificant. This may be attributed to inadequate enforcement machinery, skilled labour force, a tax structure that is not buoyant and inelastic, as well as the structure of the economy which makes it difficult, if not impossible, for others to be taxed due to their social or political status. Until proactive measures at all levels are adopted by the public authorities to strengthen transparency, fight corruption and abuse of public resources within the statutory institutions responsible for tax related matters, otherwise the negative effect and high increase in the level of debt and deficit will continue to surface in the current account balance thereby affecting the fiscal prudence and the position of macroeconomic stability in the country.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are several and growing number of literature on the significance of tax revenue on economic growth and development. The results remain ambiguous and inconsistent as certain taxes are productive when applied in some countries, while it appears as growth-retarding in other countries. In the literature, two different and divergent views are common in terms of the debate on the effectiveness and productivity of tax revenue in ensuring sustainable growth and development. These arguments are based on the positive effect and negative effect of the tax on economic growth which is consistent with the epistemological propositions of Keynesian and Classical doctrine, respectively and is critically reviewed as follows:

3.1 Evidence Pointing towards Keynesian View

From the literature, a good number of studies are consistent with the views and arguments of Keynesian philosophy and this includes the following contributions: [7] investigates the impact of tax on the Nigerian economy using a descriptive survey approach by employing a simple percentage and narration response in 2012. The result shows that, while inefficiency in the tax administration affects the revenue generation in Nigeria, tax revenue has a significant impact on government budget implementation and by extension to output growth. Likewise, estimates provided by [14] in a

study that examine the impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria from 1986 to 2010 using OLS regression model shows that, there exist a positive and significant relationship between Petroleum Profit Tax and Non-oil tax revenue and the growth of the Nigerian economy, but no relationship exist between Company Income Tax and GDP within the sample period.

Similarly, using a neoclassical Solow growth model and Toda-Yamamoto causality test on quarterly data set from 1986Q1 to 2014Q4, further evidence reveals by [23] in a study that examines the link between tax revenue and economic growth in Ghana shows a strong unidirectional causal relationship from tax revenue to economic growth. Hence, tax revenue contributes significantly to nation's growth rate. The government should, therefore, design and implement policies that improve the tax scope in order to generate more revenue from taxation. Likewise, [17] examine the relationship between taxation and economic growth in eight (8) West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU) countries using a dynamic panel data from 1989 to 2012. The study employed a panel regression model and GMM technique, and the result shows a positive and linear relationship between taxation and output growth in all WAEMU countries. More precisely, weak and high rates of tax both at short and long run do not create distortions and therefore affect the economic growth of WAEMU positively and generate income. This effect on economic growth then continues to increase over time as the fiscal revenue increases as well, hence high and weak levels of taxation are favourable to economic growth.

In the same vein, [24] examine the effects of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria from 1970 to 2011 using an OLS regression technique. The result shows the existence of a positive relationship between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. Although the variable is positive but not statistically significant in influencing economic growth. Also, domestic investment has a positive relationship with economic growth, indicating that an increase in the level of investment will eventually lead to an increase in the level of output and therefore economic growth. Apart from being theoretically consistent with a priori expectation, the variable is also statistically significant. Besides tax revenue and domestic investment, the result also shows that foreign direct investment and labour

force have a positive and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Furthermore, [12] examines the correlation between value-added tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria from 1994 to 2012 by utilising several diagnostic tests, cointegration technique and Granger causality test. The granger causality result shows that tax revenue does granger cause economic growth, but there exists a positive and significant relationship between revenue and real output growth within the review period. In addition, [9] empirically examine the impact of value added tax on economic growth in Nigeria spanning 1994 to 2008 using OLS regression model and granger causality test. The study reveals that the contribution of tax revenue is relatively low in Nigeria compared to other Sub-Saharan African countries like Ivory Coast, Kenya and Senegal. Also, the ratio of VAT revenue to GDP averaged 1.3% in Nigeria compared to 4.5% in Indonesia, though; the study further shows a positive and significant relationship between tax revenue and economic growth within the review period.

In another development, [25] study the effects of value added tax revenue on the economic growth of Nigeria covering 1994-2010 by making use of linear regression model. The result from the study shows that tax revenue has a significant and positive effect on the gross domestic product within the review period. Furthermore, [19] employed an OLS estimation technique and time series data from 1981 to 2007 to determine the relationship between Nigeria's economic growth and the major components of tax revenue. The study reveals that, though the actual tax revenue generated in most of the years fell below the targeted amount, but the existing positive and significant relationship between GDP and the tax revenue indicates that, policy measures to expand tax revenue through more effective and corrupt-free tax administration will impact positively in growing the economy.

Similarly, using an OLS regression model, [2] examines the impact of non-oil tax on economic growth in Nigeria. The study found that non-oil tax revenue has a positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria within the review period spanning 1993 to 2012. Likewise, [10] assess the effect of revenue generation in Nigeria from 2001 to 2010 using a stepwise regression analysis. The result shows that tax revenue has a statistically significant effect on the growth performance of the economy as well as on revenue generation. The implication of this

result is that tax revenue, particularly the Value Added Tax (VAT) has contributed maximally to aggregate revenue, hence justifying the fact that the tax approach has a significant and positive effect on the total output in Nigeria.

In addition, using Cobb-Douglas simple regression model and a descriptive statistics from 1994 to 2010, empirical findings from [26] in a study that evaluates the role of tax revenue in the economic growth of Nigeria shows that, total revenue significantly account for 92% variation in the GDP. This high explanatory power indicates that total revenue is an essential element as well as an important determinant of economic growth in Nigeria. Moreover, [27] examine the impact of petroleum profit tax on the economic growth in Nigeria using granger causality test for the period of 1970 to 2010. In order to achieve this, several diagnostic tests were conducted, including Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation LM test and White heteroskedasticity test. It was found that petroleum profit tax does granger causes gross domestic product. This implies the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between economic growth and petroleum profit tax in Nigeria.

Likewise, [28] study the impact of value added tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria from 1994 to 2011 by utilising an OLS regression model. The result shows that tax revenue contributes significantly to the aggregate economic performance of government and by extension to the economic growth of Nigeria. Although, the growth pattern of GDP is fluctuating under the review period, but revenue growth had a steady increase, but the growth was not as volatile as that of the GDP. Similarly, [29] examine the relationship between tax revenue and economic development in Nigeria from 1980 to 2007 using a Three-Stage Least Square (3SLS) regression model. The result shows that tax revenue encourages economic growth through infrastructural development. That is, it positively highlights the channels through which tax revenue impacted on economic growth, these channels include foreign direct investment and infrastructural development. The study also reveals that tax revenue has no independent effect on growth, but fairly allowing the infrastructural development and foreign direct investment to positively respond to increase in output.

In another development, using an ARDL Bound testing technique and VAR on different types of tax and RGDP from 1986 to 2012, results from

[6] in a study that assess the equilibrium relationship between tax and output growth in Nigeria indicate that aggregate tax revenue has a positive and significant effect on economic growth; explaining about 73.4% of the total variation in RGDP. The study, therefore, holds the view that, there exist a long-run equilibrium relationship between total tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. Furthermore, [30] posit that tax revenue contributes substantially to economic development and hence the need to restructure and reorganise a nation's tax system so as to ensure the realisation of optimal tax revenue through fair and equitable distribution of tax burden. The reality in most developing countries is that there is a limited scope for raising extra tax revenues coupled with a high budgetary pressure as a result of ever-increasing demand for public goods.

3.2 Evidence Pointing towards Classical View

In an early attempt to examine the relationship between tax revenue and output growth under the Classical assumptions, the contributions of [31,32,33] reveals the negative relationship between tax and growth. However, [34] concluded that the aforementioned negative relationship between tax rates and economic growth rate disappeared once the level of per capita income is included in the conventional regression model. Furthermore, [35] employed a Neo-classical aggregate production function on a panel data from 107 developing countries spanning 1970 to 1985, and the study reveals that taxation produces a negative effect on the output growth rate within the review period. Likewise, [36] examines the link between government spending, tax revenue and economic growth in 23 OECD countries from 1971 to 1988 by adopting [37] and [38]. The study submitted that the size of government is limited by the need to finance expenditures by levying of distortionary taxes, which reduce the marginal return to private capital and therefore inhibit economic growth. In other word, distortionary taxes has a growth-retarding effect.

In addition, [39] examine the effects of value added tax revenue on economic growth in Kenya using Poisson regression model from 1990 to 2014. The study found that a percentage change in the incidence rate of GDP is an increase of 7% for every unit decrease in tax revenue. It can, therefore, be concluded that there exists a significant negative relationship between tax

revenue and GDP in Kenya within the review period. Similarly, with regard to the effect of tax revenue on economic growth, [4] examine the effect of tax policy on economic growth in Nigeria by applying time series regression analysis from 1994 to 2013. Finding reveals that tax policy has a significant effect, while its various components produced different effects on economic growth. The result shows that indirect tax has a strong and a significant positive relationship with the level of economic growth while direct tax shows a weak relationship with economic growth in Nigeria within the period under review.

In a similar analysis, [40] assess the impact of tax on the output growth of Canadian province from 1981 to 2010 using a fixed-effect panel regression model. The study holds the view that, a negative impact of taxation on GDP per capita growth rate for the Canadian provinces exists, but this impact changes from one tax to another. For instance, personal income tax has a lower negative effect on growth rate compared to corporate income tax and consumption tax with higher negative effects. Furthermore, the study found that the significance level of the panel data variables with 5-year averages is lower than annual panel data variables.

Furthermore, [18] examine the causes and consequences of VAT revenue by utilising an unbalanced panel data of 143 countries for 26 years. The study adopted a recursive two-equation model and the result shows that tax revenue has a positive and significant but mixed impact on the economy. This implies that, while tax revenue contributes positively to economic growth in some countries, it appeared negatively related in other countries. On the other hand, VAT as components of aggregate revenue has a long run increase to GDP ratio to an average of 4.5 percent. However, the effect of VAT varies depending on the individual countries concern. This allows the effect to become negative in some while greater gains in others, most especially higher income countries and open economies. In the same vein, using OLS regression analysis on annual data from 1954 to 1986 to examine the effects of tax revenue on output growth in Taiwan, [41] shows that the total tax rate does not have a significant effect on the long-run growth rates of private output, production and consumption factor inputs. This result is due to the positive effect of consumption taxation balancing the negative effect of factor taxation on economic growth. Hence, consumption and factor tax rates have

statistically significant impacts on the long-run growth rates of macroeconomic aggregates.

Moreover, in assessing a panel of 25 rich OECD countries for the period 1970-2010, [15] examine the influence of tax on economic growth using a fixed-effect regression model and discover a negative relationship between taxation and economic growth. Also, there exists a non-linear relationship between personal income tax, corporate income tax and economic growth. Accordingly, low levels of income tax significantly influence economic growth positively and vice-versa. In the same vein, [42] investigate the relationship between taxation and economic growth in 23 OECD countries using a pooled cross-sectional data for the period 1965 to 1990. The study applied growth regression model and sensitivity analysis, and the results argued that, since there is no direct theoretical argument in the literature as to why there should be a correlation between a country's average tax rate and its economic growth, it is therefore not amazing that results from this study shows that the correlation between tax revenue and economic growth is statistically insignificant in all growth regressions in the reviewed countries for the period under the study.

Conclusively, it can be deduced from the previous economic scenarios in Nigeria that, one of the persistent problems of the Nigerian economy is the fluctuating revenue generation as featured in annual fiscal deficits and insufficient funds for national development. Meanwhile, apart from reinforcing the existing sources of revenue, it is also essential for the government to diversify its revenue base in order to achieve the objectives of constitutional responsibilities. Evidence from the literature as postulated by [43] stated that the financial or economic capacity of any government depends on the fiscal resources available to it, the revenue base of the government, and the way these resources are generated and utilised.

4. PROBLEMS AND MAJOR CHALLENGES OF MOBILISING TAX REVENUE IN NIGERIA

There are several challenges and obstacles militating against the effective operation of the Nigerian tax administration and the capacity of revenue generation. The genesis of this scenario can be rooted to the over dependence on limited sources of revenue, including oil and gas revenue and sales tax. These trade-related taxes

are vulnerable to external shocks because prices on those items are mostly determined by the world market while the exporters have no control regarding the volatile nature of the product. This has resulted to inadequate tax revenue mobilisation and continuous existence of fiscal imbalances on both the demand and supply-side of the economy. As identified by many studies in the literature including [44,21,20,16,45], the quality and efficiency of the system has contributed to the poor management and accountability of public revenue. Despite the various tax policy measures adopted in the preceding years to increase revenue mobilisation and ensure macroeconomic stability, a large number of key challenges predominantly exist in the system, among which include the followings: First, lack of efficient and reliable database system [19,44,45,46]: The problem of adequate database that will identify and capture the statistics of tax payers has demeaned the enforcement agency on matters related to tax evasion. In a case where proper records of taxpayers are not available with the enforcement agencies, tax evasion becomes easily. The desire to maximise the tax collection system is hindered by the structural menace in the economy. A larger portion of the business activities are categorised under informal sector and represents over 50% of domestic economic activities. Business operations, particularly at the informal sector level, are basically without record keeping, hence making tax assessment difficult, if not impossible. In such cases, tax-collecting officers resort to estimates as the only alternative to collect such taxes, and this paves way for local producers and other micro business engagement to avoid tax through the false declaration of sales information or refuse to register with the relevant tax administrators.

Second, poor administrative and personnel workforce [47,48,49,50]: Poor institutional capacity and inadequate personnel appeared as another major obstacle in building a solid and productive tax system. The utilisation of unskilled and poorly trained workforce deficient with technical and administrative competence to mobilise revenue is common in major developing countries including Nigeria. Inadequate machinery, poor remuneration and other related incentives are another factors identified, as most negative attitudes of tax collectors towards tax payers are connected to these challenges. Revenue staffs are not also provided with the needed regular training session to be well-informed with contemporary development on tax

related matters, as a result, the problems of unskilled workforce in addition to limited manpower reduces the productivity of revenue generation in Nigeria. Third, the problem of tax multiplication or duplication [20,44,51,52]: In Nigeria, different taxes are charged by different tiers of government as there are more than 500 taxes and levies imposed on taxpayers. This is contrary to the provision of Taxes and Levies Act of 1998, in which the approved list of tax collection does not contain some of these aforementioned taxes. This multiplication of taxes has decreased the confidence of investors and reduce the profit ratio of the private sector business and undermine the relative competitiveness of private sector growth and development. In spite of the concerted efforts of Joint Tax Board (JTB) to ensure uniformity in the application and collection of personal income tax and incidence tax, the problem of multiple taxations continues to surface particularly at the local government levels. Fourth, lack of accountability and transparency in the tax-collecting institutions [6,20,29,53]: Despite several efforts by the government to checkmate this menace, evidence has shown that revenue collectors engage in many fraudulent practices in developing countries. Corruption is very common, and most revenue collectors have two different version of revenue receipts. One version of receipt is personally designed and the other is collected from the government revenue office. At the end of revenue collection, one portion goes to the collector's pockets while the other is remitted to the government coffer. It is a common practice in Nigeria that tax evaders prefer to bribe tax collectors than pay the actual amount, in addition to the prevalence of protecting the political elites who are known as tax evaders and also discretion among the tax administrators, as this approach has further decreased the efficiency and reliability of the tax system. Therefore, measures to reduce corrupt-related practices are needed on different scale over a long period of time, although, globalisation has advocated a number of measures but the structural and political framework of a country will determine the level of its adoption.

Fifth, the problem of revenue allocation which is designed base on political favouritism than economical does not place much priority on tax efforts [20,25,44,54]: This approach, discourage the revenue mobilising initiatives and further encourage the over dependency of the federal government and other sub-national levels on the petroleum revenue. Proceeds from oil and gas

can be volatile and hence increase the country's vulnerability towards macroeconomic disequilibrium. The issue of instability surrounding the petroleum proceeds is expected to steer the economy to develop and harness other potential sources of revenue within the constitutional or legislative framework. Sixth, level of ignorance and lack of awareness [7,20,21,24]: A greater number of the citizens do not know that it is part of a civic responsibility on any nationals to appropriately pay taxes and levies as at when due, except the corporate organisations and salary earners whose tax are being deducted at source. While other nationals believe that government has failed in it statutorily functions to provide the needed basic amenities, as such, the compulsion and zeal to pay tax are diminishing. In some cases, the methods and procedures for tax payment are too old and discouraging contrary to what is obtainable in modern societies, as it has also inhibited the prompt payment of taxes. Seventh, the activities of underground economy [21,44,55,56]: Productive business engagements undertaken in critical rural areas with difficult terrain and accessibility are prone to tax evasion, as the tax administrators cannot easily access the communities. Many of these economic activities are undeclared and unaccounted for even in the computation of national income, hence the official records and data on national productivity became less reliable which may further results to inappropriate policy decision making. Apart from the difficult terrain, other activities of underground economy adversely affect the revenue productivity and efficiency of tax mobilisation in many developing countries, including Nigeria.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The current challenges and financial crisis in the Nigerian economy, as well as the global contractions, has shown enough evidence that over-reliance on oil revenue as the major source of financing government spending and other capital requirements will be irrational and counter-productive. Nigeria as a federal state constitutes of three-tiers of government including federal, state, and local government. Hence, all the different tiers are encouraged to utilise tax revenue (non-oil) as the most essential source of generating revenue to finance developmental projects and other constitutional responsibilities. A number of literature emphasised more on the need for an increase in the level of tax revenue

to enable the government to generate the needed capital requirement. Conversely, this suggestion is deficient as increasing the tax revenue to meet up with the high pressure from government expenditure will not continue to be the policy option by the public sector, as this will inflict more burden and increase economic hardship on the taxpayers and therefore, encourage tax evasion in the long-run. In another perspective, increasing and widening the scope of the tax base as well as increasing the taxable efficiency of revenue generation capacity may not be productive to encourage the desired level of output growth if the public institutions designed to ensure fiscal prudence or balances lacked the accountability insertion in managing public resources. On a safe mode and by way of recommendation, there is a need for proactive measures within the Nigerian tax system to ensure full enforcement and compliance on tax regulations, proper monitoring and evaluation of tax procedures in order to fight corruption and strengthen accountability in the public sector management. There is also need to examine the link between the burden of these sources of revenue on taxpayers and the productivity of such revenue to the government. Furthermore, the regulatory institutions responsible for handling tax related matters should be steered towards the need to re-design efficient and equitable tax policies capable of complementing public sector expenditures and hence, correct for the problems of ever-increasing deficit and debt.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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